

Language Mixing and the Narrative Interpretation of Tertiary Students

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ABSTRACT: Philippine literature is a course subject in the curriculum of the College of Criminal Justice Education which is designed to give students the knowledge and skills it requires to participate in the development of building cultural identity. Students face challenges in language knowledge actualization since the course/subject Philippine Literature is taught in their second language, English. Hence, the decoding ability of the students need to be enhanced for them to be able to analyse the text presented through literary discussions. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of the use of language mixing in teaching Philippine Literature in the narrative interpretation of tertiary students. This study used quantitative and a one-group pretest-post-test experimental research design, gathering data from the results of the pre-test and post-test. This study involves one (1) section of first year BS Criminology students, with twenty-six (26) male students and thirteen (13) female students, enrolled at Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus, taking up the course/subject LIT 1: Philippine Literature, second semester of the current academic year 2024-2025. Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used to organize, tabulate, and determine the results of the pre-test and post-test. Paired Samples T-Test was used to compare the mean scores of the respondents, based on the pre-test and post-test. Findings reveal that respondents mean on the pre-test score were 3.59 for Character Development, 3.10 for Theme Identification, 2.49 for Symbolism and Imagery, and 1.69 for Tone and Mood. Likewise, the result on the post-test score in terms of Theme Identification is 4.21, Character Development is 3.82, Tone and Mood is 3.49, and Symbolism and Imagery is 2.79. Which indicates that there is a significant effect between the use of language mixing in teaching Philippine Literature and the narrative interpretation of tertiary students. This indicates that there is a significant effect between the use of language mixing in teaching Philippine Literature and the narrative interpretation of tertiary students in terms of Tone and Mood and Theme Identification. While a more enhanced approach and further activities that could enhance their understanding of Character Development and Symbolism and Imagery.

KEYWORDS: Language Mixing, Narrative Interpretation, Character Development, Tone and Mood, Symbolism and Imagery, Theme Identification.

INTRODUCTION

Philippine literature is a course subject in the curriculum of the College of Criminal Justice Education which is designed to give students the knowledge and skills it requires to participate in the development of building cultural identity. Students in this course are expected to comprehend and provide feedback on a variety of literary texts that depict various aspects of Filipino culture throughout history. Additionally, it teaches students about the many literary techniques, movements, and historical themes that have influenced literary expressions that reflect Filipino sensibilities and experiences. It also helps students comprehend the political, social, cultural, and historical ideals developed in the literature as the basis of the Filipino identity.

Language serves as a medium for conveying ideas to others. In education, it plays a crucial role as it is the foundation of the learning process. Teachers/Instructors use language to deliver the subject matter and enable learners to understand the lesson. Additionally, language helps learners overcome difficulties in their studies. Effective communication in the learning environment requires clear and understandable language to ensure that learners can grasp the concepts being taught.

Language transfer, or bilingual language use, is a common occurrence, especially in developing countries. It often happens spontaneously during communication, where the main goal is to maintain an understandable conversation. Communication serves as a mean to express ideas or thoughts. When people communicate, the speaker's ideas are conveyed and understood by the listener, and vice versa, facilitating effective communication. Additionally, language transfer, which can involve switching or mixing the first and second languages, is frequently used to clarify spoken ideas and prevent misunderstandings or miscommunication. Another phenomenon associated with bilingualism and multilingualism is code-mixing. This occurs within bilingual or multilingual communities and involves switching between languages within the same sentence without altering the

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overall meaning. Code-mixing can include the use of words, affixes, phrases, and clauses from different languages simultaneously within a single sentence (Fadilah & Astutik, 2019).

According to Kustati (2014), language mixing, also known as code mixing, helps both lecturers and students in understanding the interplay between language, culture, and education. English can seamlessly integrate into a diverse linguistic environment, facilitating interaction with other local languages. This linguistic contact suggests the potential emergence of borrowing, code-crossing, diglossia, and language shift within the institution.

These phenomena highlight the need for teachers to activate students' knowledge and cultural background to achieve educational goals. While presenting a large amount of material can hinder cognitive development, teachers must explain the relevance of the content to students. Since code mixing can motivate students in EFL/ESL teaching through cross-cultural contact, language teachers should foster students' identities, particularly in terms of language behavior, attitudes, and recognition.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to determine the effectiveness of the use of language mixing in teaching Philippine Literature in the narrative interpretation of tertiary students.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. 1. What is the pre-test score of the respondents before being exposed to the use of language mixing in terms of:
 - 1.1 Character development;
 - 1.2 Symbolism and imagery;
 - 1.3 Tone and mood; and
 - 1.4 Theme Identification?
2. 2. What is the post-test score of the respondents after being exposed to the use of language mixing in terms of:
 - 2.1 Character development;
 - 2.2 Symbolism and imagery;
 - 2.3 Tone and mood; and
 - 2.4 Theme Identification?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents before and after being exposed to the use of language mixing in terms of:
 - 3.1 Character development;
 - 3.2 Symbolism and imagery;
 - 3.3 Tone and mood; and
 - 3.4 Theme Identification?

METHODOLOGY

This study used quantitative and a one-group pretest-posttest experimental research design, gathering data from the results of the pre-test and post-test, to examine the effectiveness of the use of language mixing in teaching Philippine Literature in the narrative interpretation of tertiary students. According to Fleetwood (2023), quantitative research involves systematically investigating phenomena by collecting and analyzing numerical data through statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. A key feature of quantitative research is its ability to present results in numerical form. It focuses on analyzing numerical data and employs inferential statistics to draw conclusions that can be generalized to a larger population. This study involves one (1) section of first year BS Criminology students, with twenty-six (26) male students and thirteen (13) female students, enrolled at Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus, taking up the course/subject LIT 1: Philippine Literature, second semester of the current academic year 2024-2025. This group of students were given the pre-test, before the administration of language mixing instruction, and post-test, after the administration of language mixing instruction. This utilized cluster sampling to identify the group of students as respondents. As mentioned by Sharma (2017), in cluster sampling, groups rather than individual members of the target population were randomly chosen for the sample. These groups could be pre-existing, like residents of specific group or students from a particular academic year. Cluster sampling can involve selecting the entire group, or in two-stage cluster sampling, first randomly selecting the group and then randomly selecting individuals within that group.

This study employed a researcher-made pre-test and post-test which were given to the respondents. The researcher has chosen two literary texts from the course syllabus of LIT 1: Philippine Literature, for the pre-test the researcher has chosen the short story "The Boy Who Never Learned" and for the post-test "Midsummer". The pre-test and post-test were composed of two (2) parts: first part focuses on the literary text itself, and the second part focuses on narrative interpretation; character development, symbolism and imagery, tone and mood, and theme identification. The researcher submitted a letter and a copy of the instruments to the internal and external experts for evaluation and validation.

After the instruments were evaluated and validated by the panel of experts, the researcher submitted a request letter to the dean of the College of Criminal Justice Education of Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus seeking for permission

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to conduct the study and gather the necessary needed data. Upon the approval of the college dean, the researcher presented the approved letter of request to the group of students who will serve as the participants of the study.

A scheduled discussion of the pre-test literary text employing English language as the medium of instruction was conducted. A printed copy of the literary text “The Boy Who Never Learned” was given to each student, each student with one copy.

During the conduct of the study, the researcher started with discussing unfamiliar words for unlocking of difficulty. Words were presented with its meaning and was further explained by the researcher. After the discussion of unfamiliar words, the researcher instructed the students to read the literary text, while assigned students are reading their parts aloud. During the reading of the literary text, the focus of the students in reading could be observed. After the reading of the literary text, the researcher conducted a literary discussion focusing on the development of the characters, most especially the main character, the tone and mood, symbolism and imagery that are present in the story, and the theme reflected in the literary text. The researcher discussed the literary text using the English language alone.

After the literary discussion of the story “The Boy Who Never Learned”, the researcher distributed to each student the copy of the pre-test and let them answer it, answering of the pre-test lasted for 30 minutes. Afterwards, the researcher checked the pre-test and recorded the scores of all the students. The researcher has recorded the scores per item.

Subsequently, a scheduled discussion of the post-test literary text applying the use of language mixing as the medium of instruction was conducted. A printed copy of the literary text “Midsummer” was given to each student, each student with one copy.

During the conduct of the study, the researcher started with discussing unfamiliar words for unlocking of difficulty. Words were presented with its meaning and were further explained by the researcher. After the discussion of unfamiliar words, the researcher instructed the students to read the literary text, while assigned students are reading their parts aloud. During the reading of the literary text, the focus of the students in reading could be observed. After reading the literary text, the researcher conducted a literary discussion focusing on the development of the characters, most especially the main character, the tone and mood, symbolism and imagery that are present in the story, and the theme reflected in the literary text. The researcher discussed the literary text language mixing, a mix or English and Tagalog Language, however, the use of Tagalog language was still minimal. For instance, in the part character development, the researcher explained the character of manong in English and only have inserted few Tagalog words for a deeper understanding as to the line “He pulled down his hat until the wide brim touched his shoulders. He crouched lower under the cover of his cart and peered ahead.” The researcher explained how manong make sure that his movement or action of lowering the brim of his hat suggests an attempt to remain inconspicuous or “hindi kapansin-sin”. Him being cautious of his surroundings.

After the literary discussion of the story “Midsummer”, the researcher distributed to each student the copy of the pre-test and let them answer it, answering of the post-test lasted for 30 minutes. Afterwards, the researcher checked the pre-test and recorded the scores of all the students. The researcher has recorded the scores per item.

The scores of both the pre-test and post-test were recorded in an item analysis format to easily identify the number of correct and incorrect answer for each part and each item. The results of the pre-test and post-test were compared and analyzed by the researcher using the statistical treatment applied in this study. The results of the assessments were secured for the data analysis to come up with valuable, reliable, and valid information in accordance with the variables to be used in the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Pre-test Score on Character Development of the Respondents Before the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	6	15.38	Exceptional
4	17	43.59	Advanced
3	11	28.21	Basic
2	4	10.26	Emerging
1	1	2.56	Inaccurate
Total	39	100	

Table 1 presents data from the pre-test measuring the variable “character development” before the application of language mixing in the literary discussion. Results show that majority of the participants scored middle-to-high range (3.00 to 5.00 points), with fewer participants gaining low score (2.00 to 1.00 points). Out of thirty-nine (39) participants, seventeen (17) scored four (4) points which falls under “Advanced”, eleven (11) participants scored three (3) points which falls under “Basic”, and six (6) participants scored five (5) points categorizing them as “Exceptional” which is 87.2% of the total population. This implies that majority of the participants demonstrated a solid foundation in character development even before language mixing was used in the literary discussion. This suggests that most participants already possessed an ability to analyze and engage with character development effectively.

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Moreover, 12.8% of the total population gained low score. Four scored two points categorized as “Emerging”, and one scored one point categorized as “Inaccurate”. This indicates that some participants may require additional support, refinement, or alternative approaches to enhance their understanding of the characters.

This indicates that the application of language mixing may serve as a valuable tool in bridging the gap, offering participants a different way to engage with the material and improve their comprehension. Additionally, language mixing, when applied, may further refine or enhance their understanding rather than building it from scratch. This is supported by Roslan, Idris and Sulaiman (2023), language mixing is commonly used by teachers because of the low English proficiency level of their students. It was discovered that the use of language mixing help students with low proficiency level to feel more comfortable in learning and sharing ideas which could turn passive learners to be more active.

In addition, language mixing could be used to effectively convey meaning. This could help learners enrich their vocabulary and foster comprehension (Dykhanova, 2015). Similarly, Hamidi and Sarem (2012) reported that when the teacher uses language mixing, students do the same. This makes students more comfortable in learning for they could understand and express ideas with the help of the language they knew better.

Table 2: Pre-test Score on Tone and Mood of the Respondents Before the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	0	0	Exceptional
4	0	0	Advanced
3	7	17.95	Basic
2	16	41.03	Emerging
1	13	33.33	Inaccurate
0	3	7.69	No Interpretation Provided
Total	39	100	

Table 2 presents the pre-test data assessing the variable "tone and mood." The results indicate that only seven participants achieved a passing score, while the majority received failing scores. No one attained a score of five (5) or four (4). Seven (7) participants scored three (3) points which is categorized as “Basic”, representing just 17.95% of the total participants. A total of sixteen (16) participants, which is majority of the participants, scored two (2) points which is categorized as “Emerging”, thirteen (13) participants obtained one (1) point which is categorized as “Inaccurate”, and three participants scored zero which falls under “No Interpretation Provided”, accounting for 82.05% of the overall population.

These results implies that the participants generally struggle with interpreting tone and mood. The absence of “Exceptional” and “Advanced” suggests that participants were challenged in comprehending tone and mood present in the literary text.

This could indicate that additional instruction or alternative methods, such as language mixing, could be beneficial in helping participants develop a deeper understanding of the tone and mood. The small number of participants who reached the “Basic” level indicates that while a few individuals have a fundamental understanding of tone and mood, the majority may benefit from focused strategies to improve their ability to recognize and interpret these elements more effectively.

Moreover, Bhatti, Shamsudin, and Said (2018) highlighted in the data collected in their study that language mixing has a beneficial role in the classroom. It is recognized as a valuable instructional strategy that could enhance the understanding of the students inside the classroom. In addition, incorporating language mixing can serve as a powerful tool for conveying meaning clearly. It enables students to expand their vocabulary while enhancing their ability to comprehend (Dykhanova, 2015).

Table 3: Pre-test Score on Symbolism and Imagery of the Respondents Before the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	0	0	Exceptional
4	8	20.51	Advanced
3	10	25.64	Basic
2	15	38.46	Emerging
1	5	12.82	Inaccurate
0	1	2.56	No Interpretation Provided
Total	39	100	

Table 3 presents the pre-test data assessing the variable “symbolism and imagery”. The results indicate that eighteen (18) participants gained a score of 3.00 to 5.00, and six participants gained a score of 0.00 to 2.00. None of the participants scored five (5), eight (8) scored four (4) points placing them in the “Advanced” category, and ten (10) obtained three (3) points, placing them in the “Basic” category, which is 46.15% of the participants. On the other hand, fifteen (15) participants scored two (2) points placing them in the “Emerging” category, five (5) scored one (1) point placing them in the “Inaccurate” category, and one (1) got

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a zero (0) falling under “No Interpretation Provided” category, which is 53.85% in total. This shows that majority of the participants got a failing score for this variable.

The findings indicate that most of the participants had difficulty in understanding and interpreting symbolism and imagery. The lack of perfect scores implies that even students who are performing well in class still had areas for improvement. Even though almost half of the participants demonstrated basic to advanced, majority still fall into the lower categories highlighting a potential gap in comprehension.

This suggests that additional instructional approaches or interventions are necessary to enhance participants' comprehension of symbolism and imagery. Incorporating language mixing in literary discussion could serve as an effective way to strengthen their ability to identify and analyze these concepts. Cahyani, De Courcy and Barnett (2018) claimed that incorporating language mixing facilitates students' understanding of unfamiliar concepts, especially when dealing with complex subject matter. This approach is highly effective in explaining challenging vocabulary, providing translations, and clarifying intricate topics, which supports both content mastery and language acquisition.

Moreover, language mixing serves as a powerful instructional strategy that promotes comprehension, engagement, and effective communication in diverse classroom settings. Its impact is particularly significant when applied strategically to address learning challenges, especially in multilingual environments and specialized subject areas. When thoughtfully integrated into teaching practices, it optimizes learning outcomes for both educators and students alike (Kana, et al, 2023).

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Table 4: Pre-test Score on Theme Identification of the Respondents Before the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	6	15.38	Exceptional
4	9	23.08	Advanced
3	11	28.21	Basic
2	9	23.08	Emerging
1	4	10.26	Inaccurate
Total	39	100	

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Table 4 presents the data from the pre-test measuring the variable “theme identification”. The data indicates that most participants achieved scores in the mid-to-high range (3.00 to 5.00 points), while fewer obtained lower scores (1.00 to 2.00 points). Among the thirty-nine (39) participants, six (6) attained the highest score of five (5), categorized as “Exceptional.” Nine (9) participants earned four (4) points, classified as “Advanced,” while eleven (11) scored three (3) points under the “Basic” category, collectively representing 66.67% of the total group. This implies that majority of the participants demonstrated a moderate to strong ability to identify the theme. This suggests that most participants have an advanced understanding of the concept, which could indicate prior knowledge, or familiarity with the task.

On the other hand, nine (9) participants scored two (2) points which is under the category “Emerging”, and four (4) participants scored score one (1) point which is under the category “Inaccurate”, which is 33.3% of the total population. This suggests that for these participants it may require additional support, such as alternative teaching strategy. Incorporating language mixing in literary discussion could serve as an effective way to enhance their ability identify themes.

Furthermore, May and Aziz (2020) stated that teachers strategically apply language mixing to elaborate challenging concepts, clarify grammatical rules, and enhance students’ comprehension. This approach is particularly beneficial to students with low proficiency level or when introducing new and complex topics, to ensure clarity and deeper understanding. Jogulu (2024) elaborated that blending two languages strategically help teachers capture the interest of the students’ interest, reduces their fear to interact during discussions, and create a welcoming learning environment that encourages participation. This approach strengthens communication and engagement while supporting both comprehension and language acquisition.

Table 5: Post-test Score on Character Development of the Respondents After the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	11	28.21	Exceptional
4	13	33.33	Advanced
3	12	30.77	Basic
2	3	7.69	Emerging
1	0	0	Inaccurate
Total	39	100	

Post-test result measuring the variable “character development” is shown in Table 5. This shows that majority of the participants scored middle-to-high range (3.00 to 5.00 points), with fewer participants gaining low score (2.00 to 1.00 points). Out of thirty-nine (39) participants, eleven (11) obtained five (5) points which falls under “Exceptional”, thirteen (13) participants obtained four (4) points categorized as “Advanced” and twelve (12) obtained three (3) points categorized as “Basic” which is 92.31%. On the other hand, three (3) participants scored two (2) points which is 7.69% which is under “Emerging”, no one falls under “Inaccurate”. This suggests that incorporating language mixing during literary discussions had a positive impact on the participants’ ability to engage in character development, increasing from 87.18% to 92.31%.

Additionally, with no participants scoring one (1) point and only a small percentage (7.69%) scoring two points implies that the majority benefited from this approach. While the increase in result is low, it may suggest that language mixing helped participants connect with the text or gain deeper insight into character progression.

However, although identifying development on characters is an essential skill for criminology students, significant challenge faced by the criminologists is their limited proficiency in the English language. This barrier is identified as a contributing factor to the improvement of score from the pre-test and post-test. The result of the study of ALSHEIKH and Masoud (2022) showed that criminology cadets did not receive any English training and that the English ability they possess do not align with the academic language skills they require. This is supported by Hunter and Bhardwa (2022) in their study “Language Barriers in the Criminal Justice System”. It is stated in the study that there is a lack in providing criminologists proper training for those who use English as their second language. Without proper training, they may struggle in comprehending and communicating with individuals who uses the English language, which leads to potential misunderstanding.

Moreover, Kekana and Montle (2023) discovered that police officers encounter challenges in understanding various English accents, identifying key ideas, constructing sentences, pronunciation, and writing reports. These difficulties impact their communication effectiveness in the workplace. Limited trainer expertise, inadequate focus on language instruction in police academies, and a greater emphasis on physical training over academic learning create barriers to effective language development. These factors hinder officers’ ability to improve their communication skills, affecting their proficiency in professional interactions.

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Table 6: Post-test Score on Tone and Mood of the Respondents After the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	5	12.82	Exceptional
4	18	46.15	Advanced
3	11	28.21	Basic
2	2	5.13	Emerging
1	2	5.13	Inaccurate
0	1	2.56	No Interpretation Provided
Total	39	100	

Table 6 presents the post-test data assessing the variable "tone and mood." The results indicate that majority of the participants got high score and only few gained low score. Five (5) participants scored five (5) points categorized as "Exceptional", eighteen (18) scored four (4) points categorized as "Advanced", and eleven (11) scored three (3) points categorized as "Basic" representing 87.18% of the total participants. A total of five (5) participants obtained low score wherein, two (2) obtained two (2) points categorized as "Emerging", another two (2) obtained one (1) point categorized as "Inaccurate", and one (1) obtained zero (0) which is "No Interpretation Provided", which sums up to 7.69% of the total number of participants.

These results suggest that incorporating language mixing in literary discussions significantly helped in improving participants' ability to understand and analyze the tone and mood present in the literary text. The increase in passing score, from 17.95% to 87.18%, indicated that language mixing may have facilitated deeper engagement and comprehension, allowing participants to interpret literary elements effectively. Likewise, Ezeh et al. (2022) revealed that incorporating language mixing substantially improves learning and understanding of the subject matter. It enables students to grasp the subject matter more thoroughly, both in terms of content and context. Their study demonstrated that students' responses affirmed their comprehension of classroom pedagogical activities, facilitated using language mixing.

According to Liveley (2019), Russian formalists emphasized the significance of the reader's emotional involvement, analyzing how narrative structure and plot arrangement influences the atmosphere and produce specific responses. Their analysis focused on the ways literary techniques influence the reader's experience, highlighting the role of form in generating meaning and effect. For Berezhnaya (2022), literature was understood as an independent system that could construct alternative worlds, where atmosphere arose from the interplay of textual elements rather than external influences. The emotional impact and ambiance were shaped through literary techniques and structural composition, highlighting the effect of the text itself.

Additionally, the low percentage of participants who scored low suggests that this approach helped in minimizing difficulties in understanding tone and mood, potentially making literary discussion more comprehensible. This could imply that using language mixing during analysis aids in connecting emotions, enhancing learning outcomes.

Table 7: Post-test Score on Symbolism and Imagery of the Respondents After the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	2	5.13	Exceptional
4	6	15.38	Advanced
3	17	43.59	Basic
2	10	25.64	Emerging
1	4	10.26	Inaccurate
Total	39	100	

Table 7 presents the post-test data assessing the variable "symbolism and imagery". The results indicate that majority of the participants demonstrated a higher level of understanding, whereas, seventeen (17) participants obtained a score of three (3) categorized as "Basic", six (6) participants obtained a score of four (4) categorized as "Advanced", and two (2) participants obtained a score of five (5) categorized as "Exceptional", which is 64.10% of the total population. Conversely, ten (10) participants scored two (2) categorized as "Emerging", and four participants scored one categorized as "Inaccurate" which is 35.90% of the total population.

The increase in passing score from 46.15% to 64.10% suggests that the implementation of language mixing in the literary discussion greatly contributed to the participants' engagement with the literary concept. This finding indicates that blending languages in discussion could be a valuable instructional approach, making complex literary ideas easily understood by the participants. This is supported by Kustati (2014), wherein he claimed that language mixing, also known as code mixing, helps both lecturers and students in understanding the interplay between language, culture, and education. English can seamlessly integrate into a diverse linguistic environment, facilitating interaction with other local languages.

Moreover, Even-Ezra (2023) stated that Explication entails analyzing and conveying the significance of symbols, helping to clarify abstract or intricate concepts for broader understanding. Symbolism is inherently linked to interpretation, with its meaning

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constantly evolving rather than remaining fixed. The significance of a symbol is shaped through careful analysis and contextual exploration, allowing for multiple perspectives and varied understandings depending on the interpreter's viewpoint and the circumstances in which it is examined.

In addition, Ezeh et al. (2022) has concluded that the use of language switching and language mixing significantly enhances language learning. Developing affective skills helps students become more eager to learn, while the psychomotor aspect provides the mental balance needed for critical and positive thinking.

Table 8: Post-test Score on Theme Identification of the Respondents After the Application of Language Mixing

Score	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Interpretation
5	22	56.41	Exceptional
4	7	17.95	Advanced
3	7	17.95	Basic
2	2	5.13	Emerging
1	1	2.56	Inaccurate
Total	39	100	

Table 8 presents the data from the post-test measuring the variable “theme identification”. The results indicate that majority of the participants demonstrated a higher level of understanding, whereas, twenty-two (22) participants obtained a score of five (5) categorized as “Exceptional”, seven (7) participants obtained a score of four (4) categorized as “Advanced”, and seven (7) participants obtained a score of three (3) categorized as “Basic”, which is 92.31% of the total population. Conversely, two (2) participants scored two (2) categorized as “Emerging”, and one participant scored one categorized as “Inaccurate” which is 7.69% of the total population.

The findings suggest that language mixing has a strong impact on the ability of the participants to identify the theme of the literary text. The significant increase in passing score from 66.67% to 92.31% indicates that language mixing helped participants have a deeper understanding of the thematic analysis.

Moreover, as stated in the study of Kumar, Nukapangu, and Hassan (2021), teachers applied the use of language mixing to explain complex concept, to build a more inclusive and conducive learning environment for the students. Lvoff (2021) stated that in formalism, literary works be examined primarily through its structural elements rather than external factors. It suggests that readers engage in its formal convention, such as theme, to have a deeper understanding of the literary work.

Additionally, Maloku and Avdyli (2023) stated that in Russian formalism, the concept of theme is deeply connected to the organization and reception of narratives, highlighting how stories are structured and experienced. This approach underscores how literature reinvents the familiar, using formal techniques to present everyday concepts. Russian formalism viewed theme not as a moral or central message, but as one of several components that could be shaped through formal techniques. They focused on analyzing how thematic content was structured and conveyed, focusing on the role of literary devices in shaping impact and effectiveness (Kuparashvili, 2020).

Table 9: Test of Difference Between the Pre-Test and Post-test Score of the Respondents Before and After the Application of Language Mixing

	Pretest		Posttest		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	M	SD	M	SD			
Character development	3.59	0.97	3.82	0.94	1.942	38	0.060
Tone and mood	1.69	0.86	3.49	1.12	7.614	38	0.000
Symbolism and imagery	2.49	1.05	2.79	1.00	1.638	38	0.110
Theme identification	3.10	1.23	4.21	1.08	5.088	38	0.000

Table 9 presents the significant difference of the pre-test and post-test after the use of language mixing in the literary discussion. Result show the mean pre-test score in terms of character development (3.59) and the mean of the post-test score (3.82) representing a little improvement. However, these data were subjected to statistical analysis which revealed that there is no significant difference ($t=1.942$; $p=0.060$) between the pre-test and post-test of the respondents after the application of language mixing in the literary discussion. Thus, the hypothesis is supported.

In terms of Tone and Mood, the mean pre-test score (1.69) and the mean post-test score (3.49) of the respondents representing a significant improvement in the interpretation of the tone and mood of the literary text. When tested at .05 level of significant difference, t-value of 7.614 shows that there is a significant difference. This shows that the use of language mixing in the literary discussion greatly helps student in analyzing the tone and mood of the literary text. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

In terms of Symbolism and Imagery, the mean pre-test score (2.49) and the post-test score (2.79) representing a little improvement in the interpretation of the respondents. Results revealed that the use of language mixing found no significant effect in the

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respondent's analysis of symbolism and imagery. The t-value of 1.638 and p-value of 0.110 reveal no significant difference at .05 level. Thus, the hypothesis is supported.

Lastly, in terms of Theme Identification, the mean pre-test score (3.10) and the post-test score (4.21) of the respondents representing a significant improvement in the identifying the theme of the literary text. When tested at .05 level of significant difference, t-value of 5.088 shows that there is a significant difference. This shows that the use of language mixing in the literary discussion greatly helps students in identifying the theme of the literary text.

These results reveals that the use of language mixing in the literary discussion can be a great help in improving the narrative interpretation of the tertiary students. With the help of the said medium of instruction, it provides more capability to enhance the analyzing and comprehending passages to have a deeper understanding of the literary text. Likewise, Ezeh et al. (2022) revealed that incorporating language mixing substantially improves learning and understanding of the subject matter. It enables students to grasp the subject matter more thoroughly, both in terms of content and context. Their study demonstrated that students' responses affirmed their comprehension of classroom pedagogical activities, facilitated using language mixing.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study as summarized, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. In terms of Tone and Mood and Theme Identification, results shows significant improvement, which highlights that language mixing is highly effective in aiding students to understand the emotional aspect of the literary text, and recognize and interpret the thematic elements in literature.
2. In terms of Character Development and Symbolism and Imagery, despite of no significant differences in pre-test and post-test score of Character Development and Symbolism and Imagery, there was still a minimal improvement in the scores. Applying language mixing still somehow affects the interpretation and understanding of the students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the drawn conclusion, the following recommendations are formulated:

1. Teachers may use the English language in introducing complex concept and utilize language mixing to provide more detailed explanations, enhancing students' comprehension.
2. In teaching literature, teachers may regularly monitor students' progress across all literary elements and use formative assessments to identify areas where language mixing needs reinforcement.
3. To enhance the understanding of character development and symbolism and imagery, teachers may refine their approach by emphasizing interactive discussions, provide additional exercises focusing on symbolism and character development to strengthen comprehension.

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